

FABRICATION OF PD/SIOC NANOFIBER WITH EXCELLENT MECHANICAL PROPERTY

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Keywords: Ceramic nanofiber, SiOC, Electrospinning, Flexible, Mechanical property.

ABSTRACT

The flexible ceramic nanofibers were highly desired due to their potential applications in free-standing catalyst supports and filters for harsh environments. In this work, a robust SiOC-based nanofibrous membranes were produced by electrospinning of polycarbosilane and small amount of palladium acetylacetonate, followed by pre-oxidation in air and pyrolysis at 1100 °C in Ar. The diameter of final fibers is about 550 nm. After addition of 1 wt% palladium, the average pore diameter inside the obtained nanofibers decreased from 18.1 nm (SiOC) to 11.2 nm (SiOC-1.0Pd), while the average tensile strength increased from 0.5 MPa (SiOC) to 23.7 MPa (SiOC-1.0Pd). The mechanism of the improved mechanical properties was investigated. We believe that the smaller microcracks size inside the nanofibers and the pinning effect by the nanoparticles contributed mostly to the excellent mechanical properties of SiOC-xPd.

1 INTRODUCTION

One-dimensional (1D) ceramic nanostructures with large surface-to-volume ratio and high porosity have shown potential applications in catalysis, energy, and environmental technologies [1]. Among the various fabrication approaches for 1D ceramic materials, electrospinning appears to be the most straightforward and versatile technique [2]. Furthermore, unlike other methods that generate relatively short nanorods or nanotubes, electrospinning can also produce continuous, aligned and multilevel structured nanofibers to expand their applications [3,4].

Though considerable research has been dedicated to the preparation and multifunctional properties of electrospun ceramic nanofibers [5,6], very few papers focused on the mechanical performance of ceramic nanofibrous membranes. Recently, Ding et al. have prepared the flexible silica and yttria-stabilized zirconia nanofibrous membranes through decreasing the size of crystal grains and increasing the percentage of boundary [7,8]. Cheng et al. believed that the existence of macro pores and the complex fiber entanglements mainly contributed to the flexible SiC nanofibers [9]. Though several ceramic nanofibers with good mechanical property have been reported [8,10–12], the mechanism for the improved mechanical properties is not clear enough. It is essential to prepare different electrospun ceramic membranes to understand the mechanism of the increased mechanical property precisely and provide flexible candidate products for future applications.

Silicon oxycarbide (SiOC), which constitutes of free carbon and $\text{SiO}_x\text{C}_{4-x}$ units in a fractal network structure, were widely studied due to their excellent thermal, mechanical and optical properties [13,14]. Recently, SiOC systems with various compositions and structures have been explored and applied in some novel fields [7], such as sensors [15,16], high-temperature microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) [17], thermal insulator [18] and Li-ion battery anode [19,20]. However, no research about flexible SiOC nanofiber have been reported so far.

In this work, we fabricated robust flexible SiOC nanofibrous membranes by electrospinning of polycarbosilane and polystyrene solution, followed by pre-oxidation and pyrolysis process. Palladium nanoparticles were introduced into SiOC nanofibers to improve the mechanical properties and the

mechanism was investigated in detail.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 PREPARATION OF DIFFERENT SiOC NANOFIBERS

In a typical process, the spinning solution was first prepared by dissolving 60 mg of polystyrene (PS, Scientific polymer production INC) and 180 mg of polycarbosilane (PCS) into 2.0 g of the mixed solvent of xylene (Fisher scientific) and N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF, Anachemia). Then, sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS, MP Biomedicals) and different amount of metal acetylacetonates were added into the above solution with magnetically stirring for 12 h. SiOC-xPd was named after the weight percentage of Pd(acac)₂ to the polymers. The obtained spinning solution was transferred into 10 ml syringe and electrospun on a Drum Electrospinning Unit (Kato Tech Inc., Japan). The spinning process was conducted at an applied voltage of 12 kV and a constant flow rate of 0.8 ml h⁻¹. The as-spun PS/PCS nanofibers were oxidized at 210 °C for 2 h in air and then pyrolyzing at 1100 °C under Ar atmosphere.

2.2 CHARACTERIZATION

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra were obtained with FTIR equipment (Frontier, PerkinElmer, USA). Thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA) was operated on Perkin Elmer Pyris 1 instrument in nitrogen at a ramp rate of 10 °C/min. The morphology and diameter of nanofibers were explored by a Hitachi S-3000 scanning electron microscope (SEM). X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were collected in the range of 10-80 ° using Rigaku multiflex diffractometer. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was carried out on a Thermo Scientific Escalab 250Xi machine equipped with a monochromatic Al K α source. The inner microstructure was observed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM, Titan G2 60-300). The specific surface area and the pore size distribution of the samples were estimated from nitrogen adsorption isotherm (Quantachrome Autosorb IQ) by means of the Brunauer–Emmett–Teller (BET) equation and the Barrett–Joyner–Halenda (BJH) model, respectively.

2.3 MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF STRENGTH FOR NANOFIBROUS MEMBRANES

The mechanical strength of obtained membranes were tested on a Kawabata KES-G1 microtensile tester as described in the previous paper [21]. Five effective experiments were used to calculate the average value. The results of the experiment were computed in load (gram force) vs. displacement. The specific stress in g/TeX was then calculated using the following equation:

$$\sigma_{specific}(g/TeX) = \frac{load(g)}{Areal\ Density(g/m^2) \times Width(mm)}$$

Then the specific stress in g/TeX was converted to engineering stress by the equation:

$$\sigma_{Eng}(MPa) = \sigma_{specific}(g/TeX) \times 9.81 \times \rho_{mat}$$

The strain was calculated by dividing the displacement by the gauge length.

3 RESULTLS AND DISCUSSION

The fabrication procedure of SiOC-xPd membranes is schematically illustrated in Fig. 1a. The homogeneous spinning solution was prepared by dissolving PS, PCS and metal acetylacetonates into the mixed solvent. Low-molecular-weight PCS (M_n=3500-4000) acted as the precursor for SiOC matrix, while an appropriate amount of PS was used to improve the spinnability of solution. The final ceramic membranes were obtained after oxidation and pyrolysis at high temperature. FTIR was employed to explore the change of functional groups in the solution due to the Si-H bonds in PCS were active and easy to react with other groups [22]. Fig. 1b shows the similar FTIR spectra of as-spun PS/PCS and PS/PCS-xPd samples. There is almost no change of the absorption intensity ratio of Si-H (2100 cm⁻¹)/Si-CH₃ (1245 cm⁻¹), suggesting no consumption of Si-H bonds after addition of Pd(acac)₂ at room temperature. In this work, pre-oxidation method was applied to crosslink the PCS molecular

adequately and enhance the ceramic yield when pyrolyzing at high temperature [23]. The pyrolysis process of the oxidized nanofibers was studied by TGA. As shown in Fig. 1c, PS decomposed completely at 400 °C, suggesting PS was removed during pyrolysis. The residual weight for stabilized PS/PdCS, PS/PdCS-0.5Pd and PS/PdCS-1.0Pd at 700 °C was 72.7%, 82.1% and 82.5%, respectively. The slightly higher ceramic yield of PS/PdCS-xPd than that of PS/PdCS originated from the extra decomposed products of Pd(acac)₂.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic illustration of the fabrication process of SiOC-xPd nanofibrous membranes. (b) FTIR spectra of as-spun PS/PdCS and PS/PdCS-xPd ($x=0.5, 2.0$) samples. (c) TGA curves of PS, oxidized PS/PdCS and oxidized PS/PdCS-xPd ($x=0.5, 1.0$) under N₂ atmosphere.

Fig. 2 presents the SEM images of SiOC and SiOC-xPd nanofibers. All the samples are oriented randomly with three-dimensional (3D) network structures and interconnected open pores, facilitating the permeability of the fibrous membranes in future applications. SiOC and SiOC-xPd fibers are uniform in size with diameters of approximately 550 nm. Some noticeable grooves were observed in SiOC-xPd samples (insets of Fig. 2). The addition of Pd(acac)₂ enhanced the charge repulsion and jet whipping instability [24], making the fiber tending to break into two fibers.

Figure 2. SEM images of (a) SiOC, (b) SiOC-0.5Pd, (c) SiOC-1.0Pd and (d) SiOC-2.0Pd. Insets are the corresponding enlarged SEM images.

The excellent mechanical properties of the nanofibrous membranes, such as flexibility and tensile strength, are crucial for the practical applications. As shown in Fig. 3a, the SiOC membrane was brittle and easy to be broken into two pieces under bending status. However, SiOC-1.0Pd exhibited excellent flexibility after crimping with glass bar, and there were no cracks or wrinkles generated. The flexibility of different SiOC-xPd samples was further investigated using the slope model. All the membranes with size of 100×10 mm were bent depending on their own gravity when moved forward. The bending length (l) was recorded upon the fiber mat contacts with the slope. Subsequently, the flexural rigidity (B) and the flexural modulus (Q) were calculated through the following equations [11].

$$B = G \times (0.5l)^3 \times 10^{-5} \times 9.8 \quad (1)$$

$$Q = \frac{12B}{t^3} \times 10^{-3} \times 9.8 \quad (2)$$

where G is the area density (g m^{-2}) of fiber mat; t is the thickness (mm) of the sample.

The stiff SiOC sample can not be bent depending on its own gravity. As listed in Table 1, SiOC-1.0Pd displayed the lowest flexural modulus of 2.23 ± 0.17 kPa, which is even much lower than the reported ZrO_2/C nanofibers [11]. Nevertheless, the flexural modulus increased to 7.79 kPa for SiOC-2.0Pd. The typical stress-strain curves of the obtained membranes were presented in Fig. 3b and the corresponding calculated values were shown in Table 1. The tensile strength enhanced slightly with the increase of palladium content in the fibers. SiOC-2.0Pd possessed the highest average strength of 33.2 MPa, which was extremely higher than that of SiOC (0.5 MPa). The elastic modulus of SiOC-1.0Pd demonstrated two times higher than that of SiOC. As can be seen from the inset of Fig. 3b, a small piece of SiOC-1.0Pd with size of $20 \times 20 \times 0.05$ mm can even support the weight of 20 g. Additionally, SiOC-1.0Pd membrane remain intact (Fig. 3c) in the water after sonication for about 10 s, while SiOC was pulverizing completely. All the above results show that the mechanical properties of SiOC-based ceramic membrane were tremendously improved after introducing of palladium in the nanofibers.

Figure 3. (a) Digital pictures of flexibility for SiOC and SiOC-1.0Pd. (b) Typical stress-strain curves of SiOC and SiOC-xPd fibrous membranes. Inset is the digital picture for the mechanical property of SiOC-1.0Pd. The size of SiOC-1.0Pd sample is 20×20×0.05 mm. (c) Digital pictures of SiOC and SiOC-1.0Pd membranes in water before and after sonication.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of SiOC, SiOC-0.5Pd, SiOC-1.0Pd and SiOC-2.0Pd.

Samples	Flexural rigidity (cN cm)	Flexural modulus (kPa)	Tensile stress (MPa)	Elastic modulus (MPa)
SiOC	-	--	0.5±0.2	289±23
SiOC-0.5Pd	0.041±0.002	6.85±0.97	6.5±1.0	302±43
SiOC-1.0Pd	0.058±0.008	2.23±0.17	23.7±4.5	618±123
SiOC-2.0Pd	0.022±0.002	7.79±3.37	33.2±8.9	466±52

To explore the mechanism on the enhancement of mechanical properties, the microstructures of as-obtained different nanofibers were compared. XRD patterns (Fig. 4a) show that the ceramic matrix is amorphous due to the low pyrolysis temperature. Two broad peaks centered at 34.6° and 59.8° are attributed to amorphous SiOC phase. Several peaks appearing around 35.2°, 37.5°, 59.5° and 71.3° correspond to the PdO (Match#96-200-2238) [25]. A small peak for Pd (111) can be found at about 40.6°, indicating the co-existence of Pd and PdO in SiOC-xPd. Two peaks at 336.6 and 342.0 eV corresponding to 3d_{5/2} and 3d_{3/2} binding energy for PdO [26], respectively, were observed in Pd 3d XPS spectrum (Fig. 4b), further proving the existence of PdO in SiOC-2.0Pd. TEM observations in Fig. 4c-4e show the amorphous structure and the existence of nanopores in SiOC. Large numbers of nanopores inside SiOC nanofibers will decrease their mechanical performance. However, abundant ceramic boundary and nanoparticles with diameters of approximately 10 nm adhering on the ceramic matrix can be found in the TEM images of SiOC-1.0Pd (Fig. 4f-4g). HRTEM images (Fig. 4h) further confirmed the small particle is core-shell structure of Pd and PdO. The partial oxidation of Pd by the adjacent oxygen in the ceramic matrix results in the formation of PdO shell.

Figure 4. (a) XRD patterns of SiOC and SiOC-xPd. (b) Pd 3d XPS spectrum of SiOC-2.0Pd. TEM and the high-resolution TEM (HRTEM) images of (c, d, e) SiOC and (f, g, h) SiOC-1.0Pd.

It is well known that the number and the size of cracks or pores play an important role in determining the mechanical strength of the ceramic fibers. N_2 adsorption-desorption measurements for SiOC and SiOC-1.0Pd present type IV isotherms with H_2 hysteresis loops (Fig. 5a), indicating the similar pore structures with micropores and mesoporous. The specific surface area of SiOC and SiOC-1.0Pd calculated by BET method is 29.2 and 51.8 $m^2 g^{-1}$, respectively. The BJH method cumulative adsorption pore volume of SiOC and SiOC-1.0Pd is 0.137 and 0.162 $m^3 g^{-1}$, respectively. However, the average pore diameter of SiOC-1.0Pd is 11.2 nm, which is smaller than that of SiOC (18.1 nm, Fig. 5b). The formation of palladium nanoparticles can fill inside the microcracks, contributing to the smaller pore size of SiOC-1.0Pd. Enlarged TEM images in Fig. 5c and 5d clearly demonstrated the existence of nanoparticles and micro-cracks inside SiOC-1.0Pd nanofibers. Some cracks were found to stop extending before the particles, suggesting the particles can hinder the extension of microcracks during the bending process.

Figure 5. (a) N_2 -adsorption and desorption isotherms and (b) the corresponding BJH adsorption pore volume of SiOC and SiOC-1.0Pd. (c, d) The enlarged TEM images of SiOC-1.0Pd. (e) XRD pattern and (f) TEM image of SiOC-1.0Pd after oxidation at 700 in air. Digital picture (inset of Fig. 5e) shows the fiber mat still kept flexible after oxidation.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the robust flexible SiOC-xPd nanofibrous membranes were successfully prepared through electrospinning followed by pre-oxidation and pyrolysis process. The tensile strength and elastic modulus increased to 23.7 and 618 MPa for SiOC-1.0Pd membranes. This work opens a new insight to fabricate the flexible ceramic nanofibrous membranes and provide a robustly stable SiOC-xPd membranes for high-temperature filters. In addition, the active PdO on the surface of nanofibers can also act as the seeds for the electroless metal plating, demonstrating potential applications in heterogeneous catalysis as metal catalyst supports.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work was financially supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (51173202), Innovation Foundation for Superior Postgraduate of National University of Defense Technology, Aid Program for Science and Technology Innovative Research Team in Higher Educational Institutions of Hunan Province. Aid Program for Innovative Group of National University of Defense Technology. The support provided by NSERC under a Discovery Grant and by the CFI equipment grant to F.Ko at the University of British Columbia is greatly appreciated.

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